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A novel chemotherapeutic approach that proposes multi-phosphatase inhibition selected using transcriptomics to achieve saturation of tumor growth factor signaling.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

Citations

1. Letai, A. and de The, H., 2025. Conventional chemotherapy: millions of cures, unresolved therapeutic index. Nature Reviews Cancer, 25(3), pp.209-218.